

Iterative calculation values in the Collatz conjecture eventually reach 1 as if walking across tightropes: A summary of the assertions presented in my previous paper and the strong supporting evidence for the conjecture
(Revised version)

Summary

The claim regarding the Collatz conjecture discussed in the previous paper is clearly presented, together with strong supporting evidence that the conjecture holds for all natural numbers.

1. Introduction

In the previous paper (Shiraishi, 2026a), the characteristics of the iterative calculated values in the Collatz conjecture were examined on the basis of numerous calculation results, leading to the conclusion that the conjecture holds for all natural numbers. The purpose of the present paper is to reorganize these findings and to demonstrate more clearly the validity of my claim.

2. Summary of the claims in the previous paper

In the following, a number of equations and their corresponding equation numbers used in the previous paper are cited directly and explained. For detailed descriptions of the content, the reader is referred to the previous paper.

2.1 Calculation algorithm of the Collatz conjecture

The Collatz conjecture states that, in the iterative calculation starting from a natural number N_0 , each subsequent value N_i ($i=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$) is obtained by dividing N_i by 2 if it is even, and by calculating $3N_i+1$ if it is odd. The conjecture asserts that the calculated values eventually reach 1 for all natural numbers.

2.2 The Collatz rope and its tightrope walking

The calculated values obtained from the algorithm of the Collatz conjecture vary along numerical curves formed by multiplying an odd number H_k by 2^{q_k} as the number of iterations increases. Here, k ($=1, 2, 3, \dots$) denotes the order in which each odd number H_k and its corresponding power-law value q_k appear. I defined this sequence of numbers as a *Collatz rope*. Each rope consists of an odd number H_k at its end and an infinite set of even numbers generated by multiplying H_k by 2^{q_k} ($k=1, 2, 3, \dots$). This rope has the following characteristics.

- (1) An infinite number of Collatz ropes exist, corresponding to the number of odd integers
- (2) The sequence of natural numbers that constitutes each rope does not appear in any other rope.
- (3) The ropes never intersect with one another.

The tightrope-walking model that I proposed in the previous paper, which makes use of the Collatz ropes, is as follows. In the iterative calculation starting from an arbitrary natural number, when the calculated value is even, it slides down the current rope to the odd number at its end. Then, in accordance with the tightrope-walking equation (TW equation)

$$y = \phi H_i + 1 \quad (i = 1, \dots, n), \quad (5)$$

it moves to the junction point of the next rope. And by repeating this process, the trajectory inevitably grasps the Collatz rope whose end is 1 when $\phi=3$ or $\phi=1$, and then slides down that rope to reach 1.

2.3 Criterion equation

To determine whether the calculated value reaches 1, I introduced the following indicator.

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n q_i}{n-1} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \ln\left(\phi + \frac{1}{H_i}\right)}{(n-1)\ln 2} + \frac{\ln N_0}{(n-1)\ln 2} \quad (61)$$

Here, n denotes the number of odd values that appear during the iterative calculation, and $n-1$ represents the number of times the TW equation is applied using those odd values, that is, the number of tightrope-walking steps. The value R is defined as the ratio between the total number of divisions by 2 performed on the even numbers that appear immediately after applying the TW equation until the next odd number emerges, and the number of times the TW equation is applied. In other words, it is the average number of divisions by 2 required to slide down from the even number that appears immediately after a tightrope-walking step to the odd number at the end of that rope. Furthermore, stated more simply, this value is also equal to the number of even values that appear during the iterative calculation divided by the number of odd values minus one. From this, if the number of even values

exceeds the number of odd values, the calculated value necessarily decreases, and it can be inferred that the calculated value will eventually reach 1 when R is greater than or equal to a certain threshold.

The calculation of the R value using Eq. (61) is performed only when an odd number other than the final value 1 appears. When the initial value is an even number on the Collatz rope whose end is 1, the calculation is not applicable. In this case, since $n = 1$, the value of R becomes infinite.

If the first term on the right-hand side of Eq. (61) is replaced by

$$R_L = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \ln\left(\phi + \frac{1}{H_i}\right)}{(n-1)\ln 2} \quad (57)$$

and the second term by

$$R_H = \frac{\ln N_0}{(n-1)\ln 2}, \quad (71)$$

then the equation becomes

$$R = R_L + R_H. \quad (62)$$

Since Eq. (71) is an equation newly introduced in this paper, its equation number is assigned as the next number following the final equation of the previous paper. The values on the right-hand sides of Eq. (57) and Eq. (71) before division by $n - 1$ have the following meanings:

Eq. (57): The nominal number of divisions by 2 required to reduce the initial value N_0 to 1.

Eq. (71): The nominal number of divisions by 2 required to reduce the total amount of increase produced by the tightrope-walking steps back down to N_0 .

2.4 Necessary conditions

As shown in the previous paper, when $\phi=3$ or $\phi=1$, the iterative calculation never uses the same Collatz rope more than once. This prevents any cyclic behavior in the calculated values, and therefore constitutes a necessary condition for the values to eventually reach 1. This is referred to as **Necessary Condition 1**.

Since the second term on the right-hand side of Eq. (62) always has a positive value, the following relation holds.

$$R > R_L \quad (63)$$

This inequality is identical to the one derived under the assumption that the calculated value eventually

reaches 1 in the tightrope-walking formulation of the Collatz ropes. Therefore, Eq. (63) constitutes a necessary condition for the iterative values to decrease from N_0 and ultimately reach 1. Moreover, as discussed later, it can also be used to determine whether the calculated values diverge to infinity. In this case, $R < R_L$, and Eq. (63) does not hold. Equation (63) is referred to as **Necessary Condition 2**. However, this condition may still be satisfied even when the calculated values do not reach 1, as long as they do not diverge. An example of such a case is when the calculated values enter a cycle.

Furthermore, when $\phi=3$ or $\phi=1$, once the initial value is specified, the subsequent iterative values follow a uniquely determined path. This is referred to as **Necessary Condition 3**.

2.5 Sufficient condition

As a result, the sufficient condition that guarantees the calculated values will eventually reach 1 consists of the following three necessary conditions.

Necessary Condition 1: The iteration never produces the same odd value twice. (that is, the same Collatz rope is never used).

Necessary Condition 2: Eq. (63) holds.

Necessary Condition 3: For each initial value, the iterative values follow a uniquely determined path.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Properties of R_L

R is always greater than R_L by the amount corresponding to the second term on the right-hand side of Eq. (62). Moreover, R_L varies depending on the initial value. For example, when $\phi=3$, its maximum value is 1.708. This occurs for $N_0=3$, which consists of small odd values ($H_1=3$, $H_2=5$, and $H_3=1$) and a small number of odd terms ($n=3$). In contrast, for $N_0=5$, the number of odd terms is $n=2$, and the odd values are $H_1=5$ and $H_2=1$; therefore, R_L takes a smaller value (= 1.678) and does not attain the maximum. In this manner, for any given ϕ , R_L has an upper bound.

The lower bound is expected to be attained when the initial value approaches infinity. In this case, an infinite number of odd values appear, and thus $n \rightarrow \infty$. For an infinite initial value, R_L can be written from Eq. (57) as follows.

$$R_L = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \ln \left(\phi + \frac{1}{H_i} \right)}{(n-1) \ln 2} \quad (57)'$$

Here, the equations marked with a prime are newly introduced in this paper, indicating that they are related to the corresponding equations presented in the previous paper. The following conditions are associated with Eq. (57').

- (1) ϕ is a positive odd integer such as 1, 3, 5, 7, ... (thus $\phi \geq 1$).
- (2) The odd integers H_i are all distinct.

The second condition reflects the fact that, when $\phi=3$ or $\phi=1$, the same Collatz rope is never used. Under these conditions, applying the Cesàro mean theorem (Katznelson, 1976) shows that the limit of Eq. (57') is independent of the values H_i , and it becomes the following.

$$R_L = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \ln \left(\phi + \frac{1}{H_i} \right)}{\ln 2} = \frac{\ln \phi}{\ln 2} = \log_2 \phi \quad (57)''$$

When $\phi=3$, $R_L=1.585$, which is the lower bound of R . When $\phi=1$, $R_L=0$.

When n takes an arbitrary value, two situations are possible: the iterative calculation may still be in progress, or it may already have completed with the value having reached 1. In either case, since the H_i appearing in Eq. (57'') are mutually distinct odd integers, R_L is always finite. Consequently, when $\phi=3$, R_L takes values in the range

$$1.585 \leq R_L \leq 1.708. \quad (65)$$

3.2 Determining whether the iterative value reaches 1

3.2.1 The case $\phi=1$

The second term on the right-hand side of Eq. (61) is always positive. Consequently, R becomes larger than R_L , and Necessary Condition 2 is satisfied. For $\phi=1$, Necessary Conditions 1 and 3 are also satisfied. Therefore, in the case $\phi=1$, it is evident that the iterative calculation in the Collatz conjecture reaches the value 1 for all natural numbers.

This conclusion is also evident from the analytical results obtained using the four types of Collatz operations. As shown in the previous paper, these Collatz operations allow a complete description of the behavior of all natural numbers that appear during the iterative calculation. Let the initial odd value be H_i , and approximate the rate of change produced by applying the TW equation as $(1 \times H_i + 1) / H_i \cong 1$. Under this approximation, the rates of change of the calculated values for the operation types included in the Collatz operations **A'**, **A''**, **B**, and **C** in the case $\phi=1$ take the values shown in the parentheses below.

Operation type **A'** ; **A'**→**A'** (0.25), **A'**→**A''** (0.25), **A'**→**B** (0.25) , **A'**→**C** (0.25)

Operation type **B** ; **B**→**A'** (0.5), **B**→**A''** (0.5), **B**→**C** (0.5)

Operation type **C** ; $C \rightarrow A'$ (0.5), $C \rightarrow A''$ (0.5), $C \rightarrow B$ (0.5) , $C \rightarrow C$ (0.5)

In other words, for every operation type, the rate of change is less than 1, and therefore the calculated value decreases reliably with each iteration. As a result, the calculated value unconditionally reaches 1 for all natural numbers.

Assuming that the occurrence frequency of each Collatz operation is proportional to its frequency among the natural numbers, the average rate of change per Collatz operation becomes 0.4375 when $\phi=1$. A simulation based on the dynamic model using this value also showed that the calculated value always decreases.

3.2.2 The case $\phi=5$

In this case, Necessary Condition 2 is not satisfied. Although Necessary Condition 1 appears to be satisfied when considering only the functional form of Eq. (57), in reality it holds only for certain initial values. This is because, when $\phi=5$, the H_i do not always become mutually distinct odd integers. In such situations, the Cesàro mean theorem no longer guarantees that $1/H_i \rightarrow 0$, and depending on the values of H_i , the limit of R_L may fail to exist (or R_L may increase significantly). Therefore, there are cases in which Eq. (63) holds and cases in which it does not. Moreover, even when Eq. (63) holds for $\phi=5$, there is no guarantee that the calculated value will reach 1. This is because the same Collatz rope may be selected repeatedly, causing the calculation to cycle. In fact, when odd initial values from 3 to 19 are used, the calculated value reaches 1 for $N_0=3, 15,$ and 19 , whereas for $N_0=5, 13,$ and 17 , the same calculation is repeated. For $N_0=7, 9,$ and 11 , the calculated value increases dramatically and does not converge.

The average rate of change per Collatz operation is 1.1875 when $\phi=5$. A simulation based on the dynamic model using this value shows that the calculated value diverges to infinity. This suggests that, depending on the types of Collatz operations that appear, the calculated value may continue to increase without bound.

3.2.3 The case $\phi=3$

In this case, as in the case $\phi=1$, Necessary Conditions 1, 2, and 3 are satisfied. Therefore, when $\phi=3$, that is, in the iterative calculation of the Collatz conjecture, it is considered that the calculated value reaches 1 for all natural numbers.

To confirm this, I examine the change in the calculated value using the four types of the Collatz operations. Let the initial odd value be H_i , and approximate the rate of change produced by applying the TW equation as $(3 \times H_i + 1)/H_i \cong 3$. Under this approximation, the rates of change of the calculated values for the operation types included in the Collatz operations **A'**, **A''**, **B**, and **C** in the case $\phi=3$ take the values shown in the parentheses below.

Operation type **A'** ; $A' \rightarrow A'$ ($3/2//2=0.75$), $A' \rightarrow A''$ (0.75), $A' \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ (0.75)

Operation type **A''** ; $A'' \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$ ($3/2//2=0.75$)

Operation type **B** ; $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A'$ ($3/2=1.5$), $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A''$ (1.5), $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$ (1.5)

Operation type **C** ; $\mathbf{C} \rightarrow A'$ (0.5), $\mathbf{C} \rightarrow A''$ (0.5), $\mathbf{C} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ (0.5) , $\mathbf{C} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$ (0.5)

From this, it follows that the calculated value increases reliably only when the Collatz operation **B** appears. Therefore, in what follows, I restrict our analysis to this operation.

The Collatz operation **B** consists of three types ($\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A'$, $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A''$, and $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$). Here, the symbol to the right of the arrow denotes the operation type that appears next. I now examine whether the rate of change of the calculated value becomes less than 1 for certain combinations of operation types. First, when the two types $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A'$ and $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A''$ occur consecutively, the result is as follows.

$$\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A' \quad (1.5 \times 0.75 \times 0.75 = 0.844)$$

$$\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A'' \quad (1.5 \times 0.75 \times 0.75 = 0.844)$$

$$\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow \mathbf{B} \quad (1.5 \times 0.75 \times 0.75 = 0.844)$$

$$\mathbf{B} \rightarrow A'', A'' \rightarrow \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{C} \rightarrow \quad (1.5 \times 0.75 \times 0.5 = 0.563)$$

From this, it follows that for these types, the two subsequent operation types make the rate of change of the calculated value less than 1. For the case $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$, I consider sequences in which three operation types appear consecutively. These are as follows.

$$\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{B} \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow \quad (1.5 \times 1.5 \times 0.75 \times 0.75 \times 0.75 = 0.949)$$

$$\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{B} \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A'', A'' \rightarrow \mathbf{C} \quad (1.5 \times 1.5 \times 0.75 \times 0.75 \times 0.75 = 0.949)$$

$$\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{B} \rightarrow A', A' \rightarrow A'', A'' \rightarrow \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{C} \rightarrow \quad (1.5 \times 1.5 \times 0.75 \times 0.75 \times 0.5 = 0.633)$$

$$\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{B} \rightarrow A'', A'' \rightarrow \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{C} \rightarrow \quad (1.5 \times 1.5 \times 0.75 \times 0.5 = 0.844)$$

From this, it follows that even in the case $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$, the calculated value decreases as long as a different operation type appears afterward.

On the other hand, when the $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ type appears consecutively, the calculated value increases by a factor of 1.5 with each iteration. If this were to continue indefinitely, the calculated value would diverge. In such cases, many odd numbers that contribute to the increase of the calculated value appear, causing R to become smaller than R_L , and thus Necessary Condition 2 is not satisfied. However, as proven in the previous paper, the $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ type does not continue indefinitely and eventually transitions to a different Collatz operation type.

Although in this case the calculated value does not diverge to infinity, one might still be concerned that it could continue to fluctuate while remaining finite. However, since Necessary Condition 3 is satisfied, such behavior does not occur. Once an initial value is assigned to a particular Collatz rope, the sequence of Collatz ropes through which the calculated value subsequently transitions is predetermined. This means that the permutation of all odd numbers is fixed in advance. Consequently, within a finite number of steps, the calculation is guaranteed to reach a Collatz rope whose endpoint is 1. In other

words, the calculated value does not continue to take finite values aimlessly; it eventually begins to decrease. Since the same Collatz rope is not used repeatedly, no cyclic behavior occurs in the calculated value, and at some point it transitions to the Collatz rope whose odd endpoint is 1. It then descends along this rope, and the calculated value ultimately becomes 1. This constitutes the scenario in which, under the Collatz conjecture, the calculated value is guaranteed to reach 1.

This scenario is also supported by the magnitude of the average rate of change per Collatz operation. This value is 0.8125 when $\phi=3$, and the results of simulations based on the dynamic model provide evidence that the calculated value decreases reliably.

As a result, in the iterative calculation corresponding to the case $\phi=3$, that is, in the Collatz conjecture, the calculated value reaches 1 for all natural numbers.

3.3 Consideration of the criterion equations

When $\phi=3$, $R_L=\ln 3/\ln 2=1.585$, and R (i.e., R_∞) is 2.1 for an infinite initial value. When $\phi=1$, $R_L=0$ and $R_\infty=1.5$.

Furthermore, when $\phi=5$, $R_L=\ln 5/\ln 2=2.322$. Using the calculational program (Shiraishi, 2006b) to perform numerical calculations, the value of R (i.e., R_∞) becomes 2.331 in cases where the calculation cycles, and 1.956 in cases where the calculated value increases significantly. It should be noted that in the latter cases, Necessary Condition 2 is not satisfied. The reason why R becomes smaller than R_L is that many odd numbers contributing to the increase of the calculated value appear during the iterative process (recall that R is defined as the number of even numbers that appear divided by the number of odd numbers minus one). These two values of R_∞ correspond to stopping the iteration after approximately 5000 steps and are not the values obtained when the calculation is fully completed.

For each value of ϕ , the conditions for determining whether the calculated value reaches 1 are given by the following expressions.

$$R > 1.585 \quad \text{for } \phi=3, \tag{56}$$

$$R > 0 \quad \text{for } \phi=1, \tag{54}$$

$$R > 2.322 \quad \text{for } \phi=5. \tag{55}$$

The values of R_L and R_∞ for $\phi=3$ and $\phi=1$ given above satisfy the corresponding criterion. In contrast, for $\phi=5$, the values satisfy the criterion when the calculated value eventually becomes 1; however, when the calculation cycles, the criterion appears to be satisfied only superficially, and the calculated value does not reach 1. Moreover, the criterion is not satisfied when the calculated value increases significantly. Thus, for $\phi=5$, Eq. (55) is satisfied only for certain natural numbers used as initial values.

3.4 Significance of introducing the Collatz rope model

In this study, the iterative calculation in the Collatz conjecture is represented using the *Collatz rope model*. Although this approach may appear to make light of a well-known and important open problem in mathematics, the introduction of this model has provided several advantages for understanding the essential characteristics of the conjecture.

By defining, for each initial value, the set of numbers governing its distinct sequence of changes as the *Collatz rope model*, it became clear that each unit of numerical change consists of a single odd number located at the terminal minimum, together with the set of even numbers that appear successively through repeated multiplication by 2. Moreover, representing these sets of numbers as ropes makes it easier to understand that each rope has infinite length and that infinitely many such ropes exist—one for every odd number.

Next, when the initial value or any value obtained during the calculation is even, the process of repeatedly dividing it by 2 until the next odd number appears is represented as *sliding down a Collatz rope*. Furthermore, the operation applied to the resulting odd number—multiplying it by 3 and adding 1—is expressed as the calculation value *tightrope-walking* to the next Collatz rope. Ultimately, the changes in values within the Collatz conjecture consist of repeated applications of these two actions. Reaching the value 1 can thus be understood as grasping the Collatz rope whose terminal odd number is 1 and sliding down to its end.

Although this representation may appear somewhat frivolous at first glance, it led to two important discoveries regarding the behavior of calculated values in the Collatz conjecture. First, the same rope is never used more than once. Second, the tightrope-walking path is uniquely determined at the moment the initial value is given, and the calculated value ultimately reaches 1 by following this predetermined path. These properties constitute necessary conditions for proving the validity of the Collatz conjecture.

Furthermore, in the process of formalizing the tightrope-walking motion within the Collatz rope model, the variable R , which is essential for monitoring changes in the calculated values, was introduced. The components of R , namely R_L and R_H , possess physical interpretations closely related to the tightrope-walking behavior. Specifically, R_L corresponds to the number of divisions by 2 required to slide down from the position reached after the tightrope movement back to the initial value, whereas R_H corresponds to the number of divisions by 2 required to slide down from the initial value to 1. Analyzing these characteristics yielded a criterion demonstrating that the calculated values do not diverge to infinity. This criterion was added as a necessary condition for the calculated value to reach 1, and together with the two previously stated necessary conditions, it forms a sufficient condition.

Thus, the changes in calculated values that arise in the Collatz conjecture can be described consistently

using the Collatz rope model. As a result, this model has become an indispensable component in establishing the validity of the conjecture.

Conclusions

Summarizing the above, the following results are obtained:

- (1) For $\phi = 3$ and $\phi = 1$, the sufficient condition—consisting of the three necessary conditions that (i) the same Collatz rope is not used in the iterative calculation, (ii) the evaluation equation is satisfied, and (iii) the path of calculated values is determined at the moment the initial value is given—holds.
- (2) For $\phi = 5$, the criterion is not always satisfied, and in many cases the calculated value either cycles or increases significantly. This is because the sufficient condition does not hold universally.
- (3) Consequently, the Collatz conjecture corresponding to the case $\phi = 3$ holds for all natural numbers.

References

Shiraishi, F. (2026a). *Collatz-conjecture-calculation (GitHub repository)*. <https://github.com/F-Shiraishi/Collatz-conjecture-calculation>.

Katznelson, Y. (1976). *An Introduction to Harmonic Analysis*. Dover.

Shiraishi, F. (2026b). *Iterative calculation values in the Collatz conjecture eventually reach 1 as if walking across tighropes*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19028464> (doi.org in Bing).

Erratum to the previous paper

In Supplementary page 19: Figure 16 in Supplementary 14,

The desctioprin “ $H_1 = 5, H_2 = 13, H_3 = 19, H_4 = 83, H_5 = 13$ ” should be corrected to “ $H_1 = 5, H_2 = 13, H_3 = 33, H_4 = 83, H_5 = 13$ ”.

Acknowledgements

The author wishes to acknowledge Dr. Mitsuhiro Nakao, professor Emeritus of Kyushu University (Graduate school for mathematics), for his helpful discussions and comments.

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